

Self-Confidence and Child Welfare

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Abstract

Self -Confidence generally enhances motivation, conviction and will power. Self-Confidence is a valuable children’s asset. It improves the children’s motivation. A sustainable sense of security in children’s mind arises from positive and productive behaviour of their self. Many of the children would like to have higher self-confidence but struggle to overcome insecurity, fear and negative self-talk. With the help of self-confidence, education and hard work perhaps children can overcome the negative aspects. Self-confidence waxes and wanes in the minds of the children but it can be maintained by educational empowerment of children. Our experience so far shows that by increasing the standard of children education excellent result would have been achieved.

Introduction

Self confident is a major component in determining success or failure in our day to day life. It leads to a happy gratifying and purposeful life. All great world leaders and teachers throughout history were internally driven by themselves in order to be a successful personality. Self confidence can start as early as childhood. It develops slowly over time. It can start just because a child feels safe, loved and accepted. Positive attention and loving care can develop self-confidence in the minds of child. Teachers can play the key role in prevention of child abuse and neglect, and when necessary teachers should support children and parent should be involved in child welfare. Child welfare is important because they require love, care and support. Child welfare is there to give equality to all children and making their lives beautiful. Child welfare aims at keeping children safe from physical and mental violence within their place of residence, schooling and community. Child welfare should be designed to ensure that children are safe and secure and it should overcome the educational neglect and psychological neglect of the children.

Self - Confidence and Child Welfare

Self - Confidence creates willingness to accept the responsibility and leads to better relationship in the minds of the children. It makes the child self-motivated, ambitious and provides new opportunities and challenges. Self - confidence improves performances and increases their ability to overcome risks of danger. It makes a child more productive and feels secure.

Self - Confidence provides the children to enjoy the company of others with utmost care. Self - Confidence awakes the child’s mind, touches his or her imagination and every way help the child to develop a composite personality. Self - Confidence creates new initiatives in the children community. Self - Confidence gives scope to develop their new talents and to maintain highest aesthetic standards. Self - Confidence turn the child’s weakness into strength. Self - Confidence gives them faith and hopes to take care of them and to guide them. Self - Confidence is like a good parent, good teacher and good guide. It helps them to do good actions and avoids poor actions. Self - Confidence develops a natural instinct for making a right, ethical decision. It makes them charming, well dressed, cultured and solve their problems.

Media and its Role in Child Welfare

We cannot imagine a true democracy functioning with a suppressed media. In India we want free media. We want a media that is objective, that criticizes, that is upfront. But we would also like to see the media looking at the serious issues, looking at the real issues that the children are facing in our country. Sometimes the media doesn’t display the issues related with children. We find that there is a very strong thrust for child development. We feel that Newspaper and Magazines that are coming out should address themselves to such more serious children issues, create awareness on educational neglect, child pornography, psychological neglect and child abuses, child trafficking and sale of children.

Media is one of the major fields which can play vital role to promote awareness for the welfare of the children. But child welfare is not projected adequately and sometimes when it is projected only the negative aspects are projected. The media doesn’t like to go in to things in adequate depth sometime the face is ruined when it is gone to too much depth. The media is afraid to bringing out the truth. Media need some more seriousness in reporting child abuses, Child pornography, psychological neglect, educational neglect, child trafficking and sale of children. If the media is really raises and brings about the real fact to safeguard the welfare of the children.

Education is the key to Child Welfare

The 21st century focuses very special problems for developing countries. In a country like India if we don’t concentrate on child welfare with the help of education we remain backward, our children remain poor and their life style remains as those of another century. We feel the key to development, the key to progress is child education. Without that there can be no development or progress. The sad part is that one is ready to layout billions of rupees for developing natural resource and new technology but when it comes out to putting out funds for children education we are not that open hearted and free in laying out our funds. Real development in child welfare can only take place if we invest more funds for children education.

If we do not impart proper education today, the child will not be able to use the new technology tomorrow. Consequentially he will be unable to become strong. Poverty will not be removed; we will not be able to break-through the shackles of backwardness.

Improving the Quality of Child Life through Education

Ever since the planning began in 1950 we have been striving towards univerzalization of Elementary education and total literacy in our country. Considerable progress has been made over these years in spreading literacy and creating educational opportunities. Time has come to face the challenge of reaching the goals of elementary education to improve the quality of child’s life through education. Raising sufficient resources is only one side of the coin. Equally important is the need for proper application of these resources and for their optimal utilization. It is media’s

involvement in children education which will make the real difference. There is no better way other than the role of the media in improving child education. Education is the only multi dimensional instrument for improving the quality of the child life in the society. Education must be perceived as a galvanizing force in children welfare and development.

Education Instills Right Values

Today illiteracy is a curse and that education is that key to opportunity and advancement, the key to removal of poverty and social injustice. Children give us tremendous joy but what do we give them in return? Free and compulsory education for all children up to the age of 14 years is a constitutional obligation. Brave children are selected from primary schools, taken to Delhi and they are honoured by giving award by the Prime Minister of India. Attending the function at the Prime Minister’s residence has its own significance. Information related to the courage, valour and gallantry of children are published all over the country through media. However other children should also know about their heroic deeds. Courage, fearlessness and resolve are virtues without which no child being can succeed in one’s life. Protecting others even at the cost of one’s own life are far greater virtues. We do come cross such children. Knowingly they put their own life in jeopardy. Here a child has been awarded for a similar act of bravery. Helping others is a duty, nothing else can excel. These children will certainly be taken out on elephants at the Republic Day Parade. The other will ask with curiosity who are the one’s being carried on Elephants. It would then be announced that they are the one’s who risked their lives to save others.

In ancient times children were taught the lesson of fearlessness. We may have seen pictures and statues where Shakuntala’s son Bhart is shown counting of lion’s teeth. But such depictions are confined only to paintings and sculptures. It is a divine quality that deifies the children. These kinds of heroic deeds should be published by the media all over the country to create fearlessness in the minds of the children.

Conclusion

As per analysis constructive education and self-confidence can solve the negative problems of children’s welfare. Primary education is the significant one that creates awareness in the mind set of the children. There is a lack of seriousness in projecting the real issues faced by the children. We can achieve the children’s welfare in a real sense that if the media really raises current issues in a positive direction and give solution. Education is the multi dimensional instrument that only can improve the quality of children welfare in all section of society.

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